

**Gun Deaths in the United States Socioeconomic and Demographic Insights from 2012 to
2014**

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It is a peaceful sunny day. You drive your car home with your family. A policeman stops you to check your driving license. It sounds like a typical story, doesn't it? So, the same happened to one young man. One the 6th of July, 2016, a 32-year old African-American was stopped by a policeman. He had been driving his car at 9 PM with his girlfriend and four years old daughter in a suburb of Saint-Paul, Minnesota. The police officer, Jeronimo Yanez, asked for this man's driving license. The young man wanted to pull his license out of his jacket, but suddenly was shot by the same police officer. The police officer used his gun thinking that this young African-American man was pulling his own gun out of the pocket. There was a misuse of firearms because of a simple driving license which cost one person's life. This story makes everyone sad, including us, so our topic is very sensitive.

Where is the limit of law and justice; and where is the guarantee that you will not be shot in the United States?

This is not a single story of shootings in the U.S. On the contrary, there is constant news about use of firearms in this country concerning The Second Amendment to the U.S. Constitution: a right to bear arms for self-protection and well-regulated militia. Based on these grounds, we are exploring a dataset called "Gun Deaths in the US".

Dataset Overview

<i>Centers for Disease Control</i>	<i>Five Thirty Eight</i>	<i>Kaggle</i>
Prevention's Multiple cause of Death database (the whole dataset on the gun deaths)	33,000 annual gun deaths in America	Gun Deaths in the US: 2012-2014 Information about gun-deaths from the CDC: Ages, gender, intent and more

Data collection process

We found the dataset on [Kaggle](#), the world's largest data science community. Data in this dataset comes primarily from the *Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's Multiple cause of Death database* (the whole dataset on the gun deaths). That's why this information is placed first in our Dataset Overview table indicating it to be the origin. Information for this dataset was derived

from death certificates of all over 50 states and Washington, D.C. This data is considered to be the most comprehensive estimate of firearm deaths.

This dataset is a part of *Five Thirty Eight* project exploring more than 33,000 annual gun deaths in America. According to the official web-site of [Five Thirty Eight](#) project, “In keeping with the CDC’s practice, deaths of non-U.S. residents that take place in the U.S. (about 50 per year) are excluded. All figures are averages from the years 2012 to 2014, except for police shootings of civilians, which are from 2014”.

Also, additional sources for collecting “Gun Deaths in the US” dataset were FBI’s count for shootings of police officers, Mother Jones’s Database for mass shootings, University of Maryland’s Global Terrorism Database for terrorism gun deaths, and 2012-14 American Community Survey microdata from the University of Minnesota’s IPUMS project for population totals.

The last “destination” of our dataset is *Kaggle* where we accessed it, thus, it’s placed third in our Data Overview table.

Leading causes of suicides

Having checked the reliability of the dataset, we dived into exploration. We figured out that two main intents of the perpetrator of gun deaths are suicide and homicide. There are many reasons that can influence people’s mental illnesses and lead to committing suicide. Thus, we looked for needed background information.

The main reasons are depression, mental illnesses, traumatic stresses, substance use,

impulsivity, loss, fear of loss, hopelessness, chronic pain and social isolation. Suicide is recently considered as a serious illness. The following list of the 10 most widespread illnesses in US: heart disease, cancer, unintentional injuries, chronic lower respiratory disease, stroke and cerebrovascular disease, Alzheimer’s disease, diabetes, influenza and pneumonia, kidney disease and suicide. Every day someone is killed with a gun or shot and wounded in the world. As shown on the Table 1 average deaths with gun is total 37603 people: suicide takes more than half of the whole people shot

which is 22926, homicide gun deaths are 13380 victims of the accident and 1298 cases involving police officers and unintentional deaths. As the data shows, gun death is a serious case in the U.S, so about two-thirds of gun deaths are suicides in America. The deterrent statistics shows that the U.S gun suicide rate is more likely 10 times higher than other high-income countries in the world. According to the [Everytownresearch](#) access to a gun triples the risk of death by suicide in America. As the information represents in our source gun suicide is more high in the states with high percentage of gun ownership. The high amount of people who try to commit suicide do not die unless they use a gun. All suicide attempts not involving a gun end with the 4 percentage of death, while with gun attempts approximately 90 percentahe of gun suicides. It is a very alarming

rate that the U.S gun homicide rate is 25 times that of other high-income countries in the world. Access to a gun doubles the risk of gun homicide. In the U.S black Americans introduce the majority of gun homicide victims. From the data Gun Death in the U.S 2012-2014, we have calculated that 63 % of gun deaths are suicides, 35% gun deaths are represented by homicides and 2% others which are unknown in the dataset.

Average Values

This dataset takes figures of 2012-2014 time period. We have calculated number of deaths for these three years:

	2012	2013	2014
Number of deaths	33563	33636	33599

Mean for these 3 years: 33599.33

Median for these 3 years: 33599

We can conclude that on average 33599 people died annually in the U.S. from 2012 to 2014.

Average values and Measures of Spread of age composition

From our data, we have calculated that the mean age of all people is from 43 years to 44 years old. People in these ages are more likely to die from firearm death. The median age is 42 which is an approximate number to the mean of age, thus making them almost similar. People in the middle of range of ages with age of 42 die from gun deaths, so it can be from gun homicides or gun suicides. The mode of the age data is 22 that means most people who commit suicide or get shot and wounded by gun are young people. The most interesting calculation of measures of spread is the minimum age which is 0, so it means even newborns are under the risk of firearm death. The maximum age is 107, and we found out that this person died from the gun homicide. The Range of ages is 107, so the oldest person who died is 107. The standard deviation of the dataset is 19.5 that means how measurements for a group are spread out from average values. The following table shows the average values and measures of spread of age composition:

Mean	43.86
Median	42
Mode	22
Minimum	0
Maximum	107
Range	107
Standard Deviation	19.50

We have calculated a 95% Confidence Interval for Population Mean for age of those who died being shot (both homicide and suicide) to estimate the true population mean interval.

	Age 95% CI for population mean
n	100798
x_bar	43.86
alpha	0.05
st_dev (s)	19.5

margin of error	0.1203821124
lower limit	43.7396
upper limit	43.9804
CI	[43.7396, 43.9804]

So, the Confidence Interval for Population Mean is [43.7396, 43.9804]

Hypothesis Testing (Population Mean)

We have found Age Classification by [World Health Organization](#):

0-17	child/teen
18-44	young adults
45-59	middle-aged adults
60-74	old adults
75-90	elderly
90+	longevity

According to this classification we want to test to which age category average number of deaths fall. Thus, we have chosen 44 as a hypothesized mean. 44 is where the “young adults” category ends and 45 is where the “middle-aged adults” category starts. So, if our Age Mean is ≤ 44 , then it’s the “young adults” and “child/teen” categories. If Mean is >44 , then it’s “middle-aged adults” category or categories above 45 years.

1) $H_0: \mu \leq 44$

$H_A: \mu > 44$

2) R.H.S. (1-tailed)

t-stat	-2.279393901
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3)

t-cutoff	1.644868744
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4) T-stat doesn't fall in the rejection region, so we DO NOT REJECT H_0

This means that Population Mean falls in the age range of 0-44 years old. This range includes two categories as “child/teen” and “young adults”. We come to the conclusion that children and young adults until 45 years old are mostly exposed to gun deaths.

Age suicide rates in the U.S

The graph shows the ratio between the amount of gun deaths and ages of victims. As it is shown on the graph, young people are more likely to die at the age of 20. More people die when they are young, so even children in the U.S are at the constant risk of firearm death.

Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/hakabuk/gun-deaths-in-the-us>

Gender Composition

Due to the the intention of the perpetrator of the crime there are two main reasons suicide and homicide. From this point, we have figured out the following and interesting observations: dmale (suicide) 54486, female (suicide) 8689, male (homicide) 29803, female (homicide) 5373. This shows that in both cases males are more likely to be killed or to commit suicide.

#OF MALE (SUICIDE)	54486
#of female (suicide)	8689
#of male (homicide)	29803
#female (homicide)	5373

Deaths by firearm-related injuries per 100,000 resident population in the U.S. from 1970 to 2016, by gender

Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/186951/deaths-by-firearm-related-injuries-in-the-us-by-gender-since-1970/>

The ratio between deaths per 100 000 resident population to the gender represented by the male and female is almost constant except for years from 1970 till 2000 years. Our data is gathered in 2012 till 2014 , so for these years the graph of females is constant. The male's graph started to

grow in 2014, so there is an increase for 1400 males during that year. In 2015 we are able to see a slight increase which is 1100 males.

The percentage of the people with/without high school education by gender

Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/hakabuk/gun-deaths-in-the-us>

This graph presents pie charts that show how educated men and women are. In the dataset, educational status of the victim can be one of the following: 1 - less than High School, 2 - graduated from high school. Using this information, we have found that female with less high school education is 11%, men with less high school education is 89%. There are females with high school education that are 13.1% and male with high school education. Despite their education, men are more likely to get injured or die by gun. As for females, they are not vulnerable as men.

Gun deaths based on the ethnicity

This graph presents our gun death data in terms of ethnical composition. 65.7% of those who died from guns were White, 23.1% - Black, 9% - Hispanic, 1.3%-Asian, and 0.9% - Native Americans. Based on this data, we could conclude that the majority of gun deaths belong to White people. However, this is not relevant until we also analyze ethnic population of the United States for 2012-2014.

Gun deaths based on the ethnicity

Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/hakabuk/gun-deaths-in-the-us>

Ratio of the deaths percentage to racial population proportion

White	66/63 (%)	1.05
Black	23/12 (%)	1.92
Hispanic	9/17 (%)	0.53
Asian	1.3/5 (%)	0.26
Native American	0.9/1 (%)	0.90

From this table we see that the death ratio is high among Black people, compared to the rest of the races. Compared to White people death ratio (1.05), Black people death ratio is almost twice higher. This means black people died twice more often than white people in the period of 2012-2014.

	95% CI for population proportion for Black
p_hat (sample proportion) for black	0.231
alpha	0.05
n	100798
margin of error	0.002601904149
lower limit	0.2284
upper limit	0.2336

CI	[22.84%, 23.36%]
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We have also calculated a 95% Confidence Interval for population proportion to estimate a true proportion of Black people gun deaths.

So, the Confidence Interval is [22.84%, 23.36%].

Hypothesis Testing (Population Proportion)

We chose a hypothesized mean to be 0.25, as we wanted to know whether Black people deaths number totals $\frac{1}{4}$ of all deaths number.

1) $H_0: p=0.25$

$H_A: p \neq 0.25$

2-tailed

2)

z-stat	-13.93089191
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3)

z-cutoff	-1.959963986
	1.959963986

4) Z-stat falls in the rejection region, so we REJECT H_0

This means that our hypothesis that Black people deaths number constitutes $\frac{1}{4}$ of total deaths number is rejected.

Correlation

We didn't have a substantial amount of numeral data in our dataset, so we decided to look for some additional sources. Having looked through, we picked a source with [GDP per capita information](#). This information was needed to calculate correlation between the number of gun suicides and GDP per capita from 2000 to 2017, which is 0.89. This is a

quite strong correlation as it is close to 1. This number shows a relation between GDP per capita increase and increase in number of firearm suicides across the given timeline. However, this correlation doesn't necessarily imply that higher GDP per capita causes a higher number of gun suicides or vice versa. The following scatter plot is a graphical representation of the calculated correlation.

Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/hakabuk/gun-deaths-in-the-us>

Linear Regression

For linear regression we decided to use data we have used for correlation calculation (again, due to lack of numeral information). My Excel is in Russian, but still we can see p-values and coefficients and investigate them. For X values (independent values) we took GDP per capita and for Y values - number of gun suicides.

Вывод итогов								
<i>Регрессионная статистика</i>								
Множественны	890,081							
R-квадрат	792,244							
Нормированнь	779,259							
Стандартная о	1009,79							
Наблюдения	18							
<i>Дисперсионный анализ</i>								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Значимость F</i>			
Регрессия	1	62213898	62213898	6,101,343	7,55E-07			
Остаток	16	16314809	1019676					
Итого	17	78528707						
	<i>Коэффициент</i>	<i>стандартная ош.</i>	<i>t-статистика</i>	<i>P-Значение</i>	<i>Нижние 95%</i>	<i>Верхние 95%</i>	<i>Нижние 95,0%</i>	<i>Верхние 95,0%</i>
Y-пересечение	-17581,9	4,987,445	-352,524	281	-28154,8	-7009,02	-28154,8	-7009,02
Переменная X	796,324	101,948	7,811,109	7,55E-07	580,205	1,012,444	580,205	1,012,444

Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/hakabuk/gun-deaths-in-the-us>

If we ignore y-intercept p-value, and only look at x p-value, then we can see that it is less than significance level (0.05). This means that changes in the predictor's value are related to changes in the response variable.

Comparison of the gun deaths between the US and Germany 1998-2015

The number of gun deaths in Germany since 1999 till 2015

Retrieved from <https://www.gunpolicy.org/firearms/region/germany>

This graph right above represents the ratio between total number of gun deaths and years of gun deaths in Germany. We can observe a slight decrease in gun deaths since 1998 till 2015, so exactly in 2012-2014 firearms were the slowest numbers of gun deaths. This is due to strict rules and the laws on the wearing of any fire-retardant introduced into the Commission of Germany. Germany has made main and strict laws to kids not to wear guns under 18 years old. While the United States of America has made legal wear of some types of firearm. The Second Amendment even serves as a legal backbone for the “right of the people to keep and bear arms”.

Retrieved from <https://www.gunpolicy.org/firearms/region/germany>

The following table shows Germany and the U.S gun death rates, so it is clear on the graph the U.S has triple the area of Germany. Of all 50 states of America, only California, Connecticut and Hawaii require permission to purchase rifles or shotguns, while in Germany it is not allowed any kind of purchase without several official documents. So, the U.S has a huge amount of gun deaths due to those reasons.

Annual gun deaths in Kyrgyzstan from 2001 till 2015

Retrieved from <https://www.gunpolicy.org/firearms/region/kyrgyzstan>

This graph right above is the ratio of total gun deaths and years in Kyrgyzstan, since Kyrgyzstan has a small amount of population, but a small proportion of 0.00001% of gun deaths compared to the U.S. Due to this reason, it is obvious that not every citizen has access to firearms more than in America. It is prohibited in Kyrgyzstan to shout at someone for the sake of security, even though law enforcement representatives could not shout as it happened to a young man at the beginning of a research paper.

Conclusion

The U.S has the first ranking place of gun deaths in the world. Weapon control is one of the very first and most important issues. In America, 88-100 people die on average every year from weapons. 58 of all the teenagers held or shot weapons at least once. Because of all the accessible weapons in America, 33,500 people die from weapons every year with a rare occurrence. It can be murder or suicide, but anyone can die from an infant to an elderly person at the age of 107 years. In America, many states do not require certification or permission to carry a gun, as is customary in other parts of the world. The U.S has the highest percentage of gun deaths compared to other high-income countries in the world. Black people die from gun shootings twice more than white people in America. It is important to mention that people at the age of 20-30 are more likely to die from firearms. In America females are 21 times likely to be killed with a gun than in other high-income countries. In our data, we found out that the level of education does not affect gun death.

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